

Direct phase function acquisition using speckle correlations

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Abstract: We capture volumetric scattering materials under two nearby coherent illumination directions. We show that correlations between speckle patterns can be converted into closed-form to reveal intrinsic material phase function, determining scattering at different angles. © 2023 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Scattering is commonly encountered when visible light interacts with non-uniform materials, composed of particles of varying refractive properties. For instance biological tissues, minerals, the atmosphere and clouds etc. Material acquisition refers to the task of recovering the intrinsic properties of these materials, given some measurement of their appearance, namely the light they scatter at different directions. The parameters we aim to recover usually are extinction and absorption coefficients, and the phase function, which determines on each individual scattering event, what portion of the energy is scattered at different angles.

Existing algorithms for acquiring scattering materials can be classified into three categories. Methods based on the analytical *diffusion* approximation consider optically thick media where light paths scatter multiple times. This allows for simple closed-form expressions describing the relationship between appearance and material parameters. However, it introduces ambiguities between different parameters and usually only reduced scattering parameters are acquired, rather than an exact phase function. At the other extreme, methods based on the *single scattering* approximation assume that the unknown medium is so optically thin that all photons scatter only once. Under this assumption one can again derive closed-form expressions relating the measured illumination to the intrinsic scattering parameters of interest. This allows directly measuring media such as smoke and thin or dilutable liquids [1], but not every material of interest can be made thin enough for this assumption to hold.

A third class of methods, known as inverse rendering, avoids any approximated closed-form expressions that describe the relationship between material parameters and measured energy. Rather, it uses paths of all lengths, and attempts to run a full, exact, Monte-Carlo simulation of the scattering process to find material parameters that explain the captured data [2]. While these approaches handle general materials, the Monte-Carlo simulation results in a heavy computational burden.

In this work we propose a technique that can extract the phase function of a homogeneous material of medium optical thickness *in closed-form*. This is made possible by exploiting speckle statistics formed under coherent laser illumination. Despite their random appearance, speckles have strong statistical properties such as *the memory effect* (ME), implying that speckles formed under nearby illuminations are correlated shifted versions of each other, see Fig. 1(a). This ME property has been exploited in multiple settings, in particular for seeing through scattering layers, bypassing very heavy aberrations. In this work we explore a very different, novel application of the memory effect, for measuring the phase function of volumetric scattering materials.

We start from a theoretical result by Bar *et al.* [3], showing that under certain imaging conditions speckle correlations act as a gating mechanism, allowing for an isolation of single-scattering light paths. Moreover, [3] derive a closed-form expression for single-scattering based correlations, showing it is proportional to the phase function. Thus, speckle correlations can produce a closed-form estimate of such phase functions.

While the usage of single scattering models under previous incoherent imaging conditions requires that the material would indeed be thin enough so that most light paths scatter only once, with our coherent approach, we can isolate singly-scattered light from thicker materials samples, where most light paths scatter multiple times.

Our approach applies to viscous or solid materials. We take as input two speckle images of the same material target, captured following a small tilt of the illumination beam, and use them to estimate local correlations. We have built a proof-of-concept lab prototype, which can acquire phase functions within a narrow cone of 8° . We validate our approach against ground truth materials and use it to measure a set of everyday materials.

Fig. 1: (a) We capture two speckle images following a small tilt of the illumination beam. From their correlation we directly estimate the phase function of the material. (b) Our optical setup using a 4f relay to create collimated illumination at varying angles, and a sensor to measure directional scattering.

Fig. 2: Speckle correlation for various materials. Left: validation materials with a known phase function. Right: everyday materials, where we use a thinner sample of the same material for a reference phase function.

2. Acquisition pipeline and results

To capture speckle data, we use a 4f system and place the scattering slab halfway between the lenses (Fig. 1(b)). We illuminate with the output of a fibered laser placed at the focal plane of the first lens, generating a collimated illuminating beam. By translating the source we tilt the illumination beam, in different angles. Similarly, we place a 2D sensor f after the second lens, so that each pixel measures a directional view of the scattering. We capture two speckle images under nearby illumination directions, align them with each other and compute local correlations. Bar *et al.* [3] have derived closed-form expressions allowing us to read the phase function from correlation profiles:

$$\mathcal{C}(\tau, \Delta) = \left(\rho(|\tau|) L \sigma_s e^{-OD} \text{sinc} \left(\frac{kL}{2} (\Delta \cdot \tau) \right) \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where Δ is the angle between illumination direction and τ is the angle at which light has scattered. OD denotes the optical depth of the volume, and $\rho(|\tau|)$ denotes the phase function of the material that we aim to extract. Thus it can be directly read from the correlation, assuming that material thickness, illumination and viewing directions are known. The results relies on an observation that despite the fact that light paths scatter multiple times in the material, the longer paths decorrelate and the part of correlation between the two speckle images can mostly be attributed to paths that scattered only once. The contribution of such paths can be computed in closed-form. In a single scattering event, the amount of light scattering at different directions is simply the phase function, and thus the above formula relates correlation to the phase function. Below we show that perhaps surprisingly, despite the assumption involved in this derivation, it can accurately match with real data.

To validate our approach we used two types of micro-spheres dispersed in agarose: $10\mu\text{m}$ diameter SiO_2 , and $4\mu\text{m}$ polystyrene. As particle diameter and refractive index are known, we compute the ground truth phase function using Mie theory. Fig. 2[Left] shows good agreement of the estimate and this ground truth, which holds despite the fact that the OD (optical depth) of the samples is much higher than 1, and most paths scattered multiple times. To emphasize that, Fig. 2 also shows that due to this multiple scattering, the total intensity scattering to different angles is very different than the phase function. After validation, we acquired the phase functions of various everyday materials. We plot two examples in Fig. 2[Right]. While we do not have ground truth, we compare a thick sample with a much thinner one for which a single scattering model applies.

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